

AN OVERVIEW OF ETIOLOGY, PATHOGENESIS, CLINICAL FEATURES AND
MANAGEMENT OF *MUKHA ROGAS* IN CHILDRENDr. Nisha^{*1}, Dr. Lokesh², Dr. D. K. Sahu³¹Associate Professor, Department of Shalakya Tantra, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.²Associate Professor and HOD, Department of Kaumarbhritya, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.³Professor and HOD, Department of Shalakya Tantra, Govt. (Auto.) Ayurved College and Hospital, Rewa (M.P.) India.

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ABSTRACT

An Ayurvedic viewpoint considers that health is not simply the absence of an ailment but it is a state or dynamic balance between a person's mind, body and environment. This is a comprehensive paradigm to reflect the holistic nature of *Mukha Roga*, or oral diseases, as well as the idea that food and lifestyle habits contribute greatly to the initiation and/or exacerbation and/or healing of oral diseases. The soft and hard palate, tongue, gingiva, oral mucosa, dentition, periodontium, and salivary glands are the oral manifestations of *Mukha Roga*. Important *Aaharaja Nidana* of *Mukha Roga* includes *Matsya*, *Mahisha Mamsa*, *Varaha Mamsa*, *Masha*, *Dadhi* and *Ikshurasa* etc. The majority of these foods mostly include *Madhura* and *Amla Rasa*, which causes *Kapha dominating Doshas* to become vitiated. *Doshas Prakopa* causes *Rakta Dushti*, which in turn leads to the development of *Mukha Roga* in children. This article focuses on the therapeutic properties of various dietary substances that can be used as both nutrients and targeted medicines when added to the diet within an Ayurvedic framework. In addition, Ayurvedic treatments such as *Nasya* and *Gandusha* can detoxify the body on a local and systemic level, thereby supports in healing and regeneration of tissues and enhancement of immunity.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Mukha Roga*, *Oral cavity*, *Gandusha*, *Nasya*, *Balaroga*.**INTRODUCTION**

Mukha as defined in Ayurveda; is one of the *Bahirmukha Srotas* and is considered to be a significant part of the *Urdhwajatru*. *Mukha* acts as the entrance to our digestive tract and is a critical indicator of general health in children. *Mukha* is composed of various anatomical components including *Oshtha*, *Dantamula*, *Danta*, *Jihva*, *Talu* and *Gala*. *Mukha* can develop a wide range of disorders termed as *Muha Roga* in Ayurveda. The symptoms of these diseases may be seen within or around the *Mukha* such as; lips, oral mucosa, gingiva, teeth; salivary glands and tongue, etc. Poor oral hygiene, minor cuts or trauma to the tissues while chewing or cleaning teeth, self-inflicted injuries can allow microorganisms to enter the blood stream *via* openings in oral mucosa. Additionally, the inflamed tissues caused

by periodontal disease could lead to worsening of already existing systemic illnesses. The poor oral hygiene makes children most susceptible object for various *Muha Roga* as depicted in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1: Various Types of *Mukha Roga*.

The increase in oral disorders in children can be attributed to the effects of modern diets and lifestyle changes, etc. In this regards Ayurveda described specific *Pathya Ahara* such as *Kulatha*, *Mudga* and *Patola*, etc. The balance diets and life style pattern helps to assist in preserving oral health and prevent pathogenesis of *Muha Roga*. Appropriate procedures such as *Gandusha*, *Kavala*

and *Nasya* also help to maintain or improve oral health by encouraging oral hygiene, preventing the progression of oral disease and promoting tissue regeneration of damaged tissues. **Table 1**, depicted general aspects and treatment approaches of some common *Muha Roga* observes in children.

Table 1: Mukha Roga in Children.

<i>Mukha Roga</i>	<i>Lakshana</i>	<i>Nidana</i>	<i>Chikitsa</i>
<i>Mukha Paka</i>	Redness, excessive salivation, irritability and burning sensation	Excess <i>Katu</i> , <i>Lavana ahara</i> ; <i>Mandagni</i> ; <i>Ama</i> ; <i>pitta prakopa</i>	<i>Vata Anulomana</i> ; Application with <i>Ghrita</i> , mouth wash of <i>Tikta</i> drugs.
<i>Mukha Roga</i>	<i>Lakshana</i>	<i>Nidana</i>	<i>Chikitsa</i>
<i>Upajihvika</i>	Swelling, ulcers, pain, difficulty in speech and burning sensation	Poor oral hygiene; <i>Kapha-pitta prakopa</i> ; excess <i>Madhura</i> and <i>Abhishyandi ahara</i>	<i>Tikta and Kashaya rasa drugs</i> ; <i>Pratisarana with riphala</i> ; tongue cleaning and <i>Kapha-pitta shamana diet</i>
<i>Danta and Dantamula Roga</i>	Swollen and bleeding gums, dental caries, bad breath and toothache	Poor oral hygiene; sweets and sticky food; <i>Kapha prakopa</i> and <i>Mandagni</i>	<i>Kapha shamana</i> ; <i>Rakta shodhana</i> ; oral hygiene; <i>Pratisarana with Kashaya drugs</i> .
<i>Talu Roga</i>	Inflammation, pain, ulceration, burning and difficulty in swallowing	<i>Pitta prakopa</i> ; hot food; infections; <i>Mandagni</i> and trauma	<i>Pitta shamana</i> ; application of <i>Ghrita</i> ; mouth wash, cooling diet and avoiding spicy food.
<i>Oshtha Roga</i>	Cracks of lips, dryness, swelling, pain and bleeding	<i>Vata prakopa</i> with <i>Pitta</i> ; dehydration; lip licking and mouth breathing, etc.	<i>Vata-pitta shamana</i> ; local application of <i>Ghrita</i> , <i>Taila</i> or honey; hydration and <i>Madhura ahara</i> .
<i>Kapha Pradhana Mukha Roga</i>	Whitish coating in mouth, excessive salivation, heaviness.	<i>Madhura</i> , <i>Guru</i> , milk and curd; poor oral hygiene; <i>Mandagni</i> .	<i>Ama pachana</i> ; <i>Tikta</i> , <i>Kashaya rasa drugs</i> ; light and warm diet and mouth cleaning.

Diagnosis of *Muha Roga*

To examine a patient's oral cavity, the clinician should first visually inspect it and then palpate any pertinent structures. Looking for visible signs of disease will yield valuable information about abnormal findings including mucosal inflammation, signs of infection (swollen & discolored), cavities, swollen lymph nodes, bleeding and mobile teeth, etc.

Nidana for Muha Roga in Children

मात्स्य-माहिष-वाराह-पिशितम्, आमक-मूलकम्
माष-सूप-दधि-क्षीर-सुक्त-इक्षु-रस-फणितम्॥१॥
अवाक्-शय्याम् च भजतः, द्विषतः दन्त-धावनम्
धूम-च्छर्दन-गण्डूष-अनुचितम् च सिरा-व्यधम्॥२॥
कृद्वाः श्लेष्म-उल्बणा दोषाः कुर्वन्ति अन्तर्मुखं गदान्॥ (अ.ह.उ.21/3)

✓ Important *Aaharaja Nidana* of *Mukha Roga* is defined as excessive consumption of *Matsya*, *Varaha Mamsa*, *Masha*, *Dadhi*, *Shukta* and *Phanita*.

✓ *Avak Shayya*, *Dwishata Dantadhavana*, defective *Dhumapana*, improper *Gandusha* and improper *Siravyadha*.

Lakshana

Pichhhila, *Manda Ruk* and rigidity are characteristics along with swelling. *Muha Roga* in children manifested as *Prapaka*, *Toda*, *Daha* and *Shotha*. *Ragavata*, *Galoparodhai* and *Asyavairasya* are other symptoms of oral diseases.

Samprapti

Agnimandya, *Kapha Dosha Prakopa* and *Rakta Dushti* are caused by an excessive intake of *Madhura*, *Amla*, and *Lavana Ras* dominated foods, *Snigdha* and *Abhishyandi Ahara* and poor dental hygiene vitiates *Doshas* which further experience *Sthana Sanshraya* and causes pathogenesis of *Mukha Rogas*. Since the mouth cavity is the *Sthana* of *Bodhaka Kapha* which mainly vitiates by etiological causes. This is the main contributors to *Vikriti*, which results in *Kapha-pradhana Mukha Rogas*.

Chikitsa Sutra of Mukha Rogas

Kapha and *Rakta Dushti* pacifying approaches are recommended for *Mukha Rogas* because *Kapha* and *Rakta Dushti* are prevalent in these conditions. *Koshtha Shuddhi*, *Kavala*, *Gandusha*, *Nasya* and *Dhumapana* are further therapeutic techniques suggested to treat *Mukha Rogas* in children. For the treatment of *Mukha Rogas*, *Acharya* advises *Pradhmana Nasya*, *Lekhana* and *Tridosha-shamaka Ahara*.

Pathya of Mukha Rogas

The predominant diets of *Tikta* and *Katu Rasa*, *Yava*, *Mudga*, *Karavellaka*, *Parvala*, *Komala Mulaka* and *Tambula* are regarded as *Pathya*. Particularly helpful are diets and routines with *Kapha* and *Rakta Shodhana* qualities.

Apathya of Mukha Rogas

Excessive consumption of *Guru*, *Ruksha*, and *Kathina* meals, *Abhishyandi Ahara*, *Matsya*, *Dadhi*, *Kshira* and *Amla Rasa* dominating substances, *Diwaswapna*, cold water and *Adhomukha Shayana* should be avoided.

Modern Aspect of Mukha Roga (Oral Diseases)

According to modern aspect, these conditions comes under the category of oral diseases, involving the pathological condition of gums, teeth, palate, oral mucosa and lips, etc.

Etiology

- ✚ Sugar intake
- ✚ Improper oral hygiene
- ✚ Tobacco or smoking hazardous
- ✚ Nutritional deficiencies specially Vitamin B-complex and Vitamin C deficiency
- ✚ Bacterial plaque accumulation

The primary cause of oral disease is the action of microorganisms in dental plaque. One type of oral bacteria, *Streptococcus mutans*, metabolizes sugars from food, producing acid as a by-product. This acid leads to demineralization of the outer layer of the tooth, resulting in cavities. The continued accumulation of dental plaque along the gum line creates inflammation of the gingiva. Once the gingivitis is established, if left untreated, it can progress to periodontitis, resulting in the loss of supporting tissues. Additional problems can develop from long-term irritation or untreated infection of the mouth, such as ulcerated mucous membranes or mucosal lesions. Long-term inflammation may create tissue damage and possibly lead to systemic problems or diseases of the body.

Ayurveda and Modern Correlation

There are many conditions or diseases of *Mukha Roga* in Ayurveda that compare to current diagnostic terms. *Dantashoola* can be correlated to toothache or pulpitis; *Dantapupputaka* having similarity to dental abscess; *Sheetada* is related to the gingivitis; *Mukhapaka* possess symptomatic similarity with stomatitis/mucositis; *Oshta*

Roga can be correlated to cheilitis or angular cheilitis and *Gandamala* possess similarity with lymphadenitis. From a contemporary perspective, microbial infection, inflammation, malnutrition, and bad lifestyle choices are the main causes of oral disease. Medical sciences suggested teeth cleaning, brushing twice a day and getting regular dental checkups as preventive and treatment measures.

CONCLUSION

The primary cause of *Mukha Rogas* is *Dosha* imbalance brought on by improper food, bad dental hygiene, *Mandagni* and *Ama* development. Burning, redness, and ulceration are signs of *Pitta* dominance; heaviness, coating, and excessive salivation are signs of *Kapha* dominance; and dryness, cracks, and discomfort are signs of *Vata* involvement. Therefore, *Nidana parivarjana*, *Agni* restoration, *Dosha-shamana* therapy and oral hygiene maintenance are all important components of effective management. In addition to proper dietary control, local treatments like *Pratisarana*, *Kavala*, *Gandusha*, and the use of *Ghrita* or *Tikta-Kashaya* medications are essential for preventing recurrence and nurturing dental health. *Pitta Shamaka*, *Shothahara*, *Vedanasthapana*, *Vrana Shodhana*, *Vrana Ropana*, *Rakta Prasadana* and *Mamsa Dhatu Pushti Kara* measures should be the main focus of *Mukha Rogas'* line of management.

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